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CASE OF MILL'S SYNDROME AS A VARIANT OF ATYPICAL ALS IN A CENTRAL ASIAN PATIENT

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Abstract: Mill's syndrome is an atypical variant of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) characterized by progressive, idiopathic motor neuron damage. This syndrome presents with an initial unilateral impairment in the lower limb, which then progresses to the ipsilateral upper limb before affecting the contralateral limbs.

In this case, we describe a patient with Mill's syndrome whose symptoms first appeared in the left leg. After one year, the symptoms progressed to the left arm, followed by the right leg and arm. Three months later, bulbar symptoms emerged. MRI examination at our clinic revealed periventricular hyperintense foci in T2/FLAIR mode, which did not correlate with the patient's condition. MRI scans of the cervical and thoracic spinal cord showed no pathological changes. Electromyography (EMG) of the legs and arms demonstrated generalized motor neuron damage with reinnervation-denervation processes.

In conclusion, Mill's syndrome and possibly other atypical variants of ALS may be more common in the Central Asian population than previously assumed, yet they remain underdiagnosed and rarely documented. Moreover, incidental MRI findings, such as those in our patient, may be asymptomatic and should not mislead specialists in diagnosis.

Key words: Mill's syndrome, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), motor neuron, hemiplegia, N-shaped progression.

INTRODUCTION

Atypical ALS syndromes have different clinical variants characterized by a variety of onset symptoms and clinical manifestations. As a rule, they manifest with signs of motor neuron damage. Atypical ALS variants include Primary Lateral Sclerosis, Progressive Bulbar Palsy, Flail-Arm Syndrome (Vulpien-Bernhardt Syndrome), Flail-Leg Syndrome and the Pseudopolyneuritic Variant, Facial Onset Sensory and Motor Neuronopathy (FOSMN) Syndrome, O'Sullivan-McLeod Syndrome, Mill's Syndrome (Hemiplegic Variant), FEWDON-MND, Progressive Muscular Atrophy, and special clinical situations in MND/ALS [2]. All the above syndromes have specific clinical features.

LITERATURE REVIEW

We recognize the type of motor neuron pathology syndromes according to their clinical characteristics. Mill's syndrome is a rare acquired motor neuron disorder characterized by slowly progressive, unilateral,

ascending (rarely descending) hemiplegia associated with unilateral or asymmetric pyramidal signs [3]. Upper motor neuron damage predominates in this syndrome. Mill's syndrome was first described by the American neurologist Charles Karsner Mills in 1900 (1845–1930), who identified eight cases of this syndrome in the same year. The syndrome is characterized by limb asymmetry in paresis, with the lower limb being much more severely affected than the upper limb. The clinical features support its classification within the spectrum of ALS. Mill's syndrome is characterized by heterogeneity in progression, i.e., an N-shaped progression [1].

A review of the PubMed database has documented many cases where the disease began in the upper limb but did not meet the criteria for Mill's syndrome. In clinical practice, atypical ALS syndromes are often misdiagnosed as multiple sclerosis, progressive encephalomyelitis, or myelitis. In our case, the diagnosis was also delayed for several months.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study presents a clinical case of Mill's syndrome as a variant of atypical amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) in a Central Asian patient. A comprehensive clinical, neurological, and electrophysiological examination was conducted to assess motor function impairment and disease progression.

Standard diagnostic criteria for ALS were applied, alongside brain and spinal MRI to exclude other potential neurological disorders. Electromyography (EMG) was performed to evaluate motor neuron degeneration. Additionally, genetic testing was conducted to rule out hereditary ALS-related mutations.

The patient's medical history, symptoms, and disease progression were analyzed in comparison with previously reported cases of Mill's syndrome.

A literature review was performed to contextualize findings within the broader spectrum of atypical ALS presentations. Ethical approval was obtained, and the patient provided informed consent for participation and publication of findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Case: Patient A, 63 years old, complains of weakness in both arms and legs, more pronounced on the left side, as well as speech and swallowing disorders. The illness has been progressing for one year. The patient describes the onset of the disease as weakness in the left leg and impaired walking. After 4–5 months, the weakness spread to the left arm. Three months before admission to our clinic, he experienced weakness in the right leg along with speech and swallowing difficulties.

The patient underwent multiple MRI scans of the brain and was diagnosed with “**chronic cerebral ischemia.**” Clinical examination revealed central paresis of the facial nerve on the left side. Bulbar symptoms, including dysarthria, dysphagia, and a decreased palatal reflex, were observed. Tetraparesis was identified, predominantly affecting the left arm and leg. Muscle strength was rated as 2/3 in the left limbs and 3/5 in the right limbs. Hyperreflexia was present in all tendon reflexes bilaterally, and Babinski's sign was positive on both sides. Significant muscle atrophy was noted in both legs and the left arm. No sensory disturbances, cerebellar symptoms, or cognitive impairment were detected.

Laboratory tests, including a general blood test, biochemical test, coagulogram, RW, and CRP, were conducted. Instrumental examinations such as MSCT of the chest and abdominal organs, ultrasound of internal organs, endoscopic examination of the gastrointestinal tract, and colonoscopy did not reveal any oncological formations, effectively ruling out paraneoplastic syndromes. MRI of the brain showed vascular focal changes in the white matter, which may explain the central paresis of the facial nerve but did not account for the other symptoms (Fig. 1). The spinal cord appeared normal, without pathological changes (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. The central paresis of the facial nerve.

Figure 2. The spinal cord appeared normal, without pathological changes.

Electroneuromyography revealed signs of damage to the central and peripheral motor neurons, which confirmed the clinically identified signs characteristic of ALS according to the El Escorial criteria (Diagram 1, 2, 3, 4; Table 1, 2, 3).

Diagram 1

SNC

Diagram 2

Table 1. SNC - Sensory Nerves.

SNC - Sensory Nerves					
	Segment	LAT [ms]	AMP [µV]	CV [m/s]	DIST [mm]
Median-Digit II Right	Wrist - Digit II	3.9	28.0	56	140
Median-Digit II Left	Wrist - Digit II	3.7	8.6	41	120
Ulnar-Digit V Right	Wrist - Digit V	3.5	22.5	45	120
Ulnaris Left	Palm - Wrist / Dig IV - Wrist / Dig V - Wrist	1.8 / -- / --	1.4 / -- / --	-- / -- / --	-- / -- / --

Diagram 3

Table 2. F-Wave.

F-Wave					
	M-Latency [ms]	M-Amplitude [mV]	F Min [ms]	F - M [ms]	F / M [%]
Medianus Right	4.5	4.4	29.4	33.5	100
Ulnaris Left	3.1	1.5	--	--	0

Table 3. EMG - IPTA.

EMG - IPTA				
	Turns [Hz]	Amplitude [μ V]	NT/MA	MA/NT
Ext dig communis Left	347	623	0.6	1.8

Diagram 4.

In this case, we present the experience of one patient with Mill's syndrome, with a one-year duration of the disease. All clinical and paraclinical examinations of the patient produced identical results to those described in published reports on similar clinical cases of Mill's syndrome. The chronological order of symptom development was as follows: pyramidal tract lesion starting from the left leg, then progressing to the left arm and right leg, and eventually affecting the motor cranial nerves, leading to the development of bulbar symptoms. The predominant symptoms indicated upper motor neuron damage. EMG examination showed pathological discharges in both central and peripheral motor neurons. The absence of lesions on MRI of the brain and spinal cord, which could explain the patient's condition, suggests an atypical variant of ALS. The patient was treated according to international ALS management guidelines, with a slow improvement in their condition.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Mill's syndrome represents another case of atypical ALS diagnosed in a patient of Central Asian origin. The disease progressed for one year before the correct diagnosis was made. Diagnosing rare neurological conditions such as atypical ALS can be challenging and time-consuming. MRI findings may vary and may not always explain the clinical changes observed in patients.

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